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Lehrkustdidaktik and its Potential for Vocational Didactics

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the German didactical theory *Lehrkustdidaktik* (The-art-of-teaching) and its potential to enrich vocational didactics. A brief outline is given of the central conceptual scheme of The-art-of-teaching: its exemplary-genetic-dramatic approach to pedagogical cases. Following this two cases from vocational didactics are presented and discussed from the perspective of The-art-of-teaching. In conclusion it is argued that The-art-of-teaching is a didactical theory well suited to enrich vocational didactics and, in turn, to demonstrate the general educational value of some pedagogical cases taken from the vocational field.

Keywords

lehrkustdidaktik, the-art-of-teaching, vocational didactics, vocational bildung

Background

The German didactical research tradition *Lehrkustdidaktik* (mostly translated as “the art of teaching”) has grown from the Bildung-oriented didactics of Martin Wagenschein (eg. Aeschlimann, 1999; Berg, 2003, 2004, 2009; Wagenschein, 1991). Central to it is the development of so-called *Lehrstücke* (pedagogical cases). These cases are meant to engage with a particularly rich subject matter, a “timeless theme from our history”, something that holds an unusually strong potential to develop deeper understanding in a subject and its context. As a method for this a so-called exemplary-genetic-dramatic approach is used where the case that is developed focuses on some exemplary topic (ie. a topic of unusual pedagogical richness), explores its history and how we have understood it in the past as well as present. Finally, the dramatic element emphasizes the compositional aspect, that this case be in a sense “staged” by the teacher in such a way as to involve the students in a process of exploration and experience.

A typical pedagogical case that has been well researched and repeatedly “staged” (Emden & Gerwig, 2020) is based on the famous physicist Michael Faradays lectures for children and youth, *The chemical history of a candle*. In these lectures Faraday uses a candle to explore the circulation of carbon but in such a way as to unlock for the participants the richest and deepest understanding of the subject-matter. Over the years a wide repertoire of didactical cases has developed within this practice-oriented research tradition, many as the center of doctoral theses in education.

In evaluating the work done within the “art of teaching” school of didactics the well-known German scholar of education, Wolfgang Klafki wrote (in the foreword to Berg & Schulze, 1997, p. 14f., my translation):

For me it is beyond any doubt that the concept proposed in “the art of teaching” is an original contribution to contemporary didactics. ... As far as I know there is, within German didactics, no other school that has realized the oft raised need of a cooperation between educational theory and educational practice. This holds with regards to scope, the long period of time during which research has been conducted and the width of participants from practitioner to researcher. Above all it is the intensity in the detailed and repeated planning, the “dramatic” staging and the variations that spring from this and give rise to ever new ways of enacting the “piece”.

In any education concerned with the development of deeper understanding among students, with a preparation for engaged lifelong learning as well as transitions between vocational education, work, and higher education this approach warrants interest. However, for the most part this school of didactics has remained a German-speaking affair and, even more relevant to the present context, there are no discussions or didactical cases that the author of this paper is aware of, where vocational didactics are included in “the art of teaching”. This despite many vocational tasks harboring promising potential in this direction (see Tyson, 2017 for some initial discussions within a similar framework but without explicit connections).

Aim

The aim of this paper is to:

- a) Provide a brief theoretical look at “the art of teaching” discussing its core concepts and their relevance for vocational didactics.
- b) Present two empirical case studies where vocational tasks have been used in an exemplary-genetic-dramatic way and to discuss how these could function as templates for further research and practice in the field.

“The art of teaching” – theoretical foundations and relevance for vocational didactics

“The art of teaching” is a school of didactics originating with the German professor of science-didactics Martin Wagenschein (1896-1988) (cf. Westbury et al. 2000, for an English introduction). He developed a perspective on educating for understanding that proceeded from the exemplary, what is today called a “Lehrstück” or pedagogical case¹ (Berg 2003).

Wagenschein was mainly involved in the didactics of natural science and mathematics where he advocated for what has become known as a Socratic-genetic-exemplary method – in later varieties revised to an exemplary-genetic-dramatic.

An exemplary pedagogical case is chosen because it places one of “humanities star-moments” (*Sternstunden der Menschheit*, after the famous novel by Stefan Zweig of the same title), or epochally typical themes of humanity.

The genetic element is about going back to one of the historical origins of a phenomenon, in science often the time when the phenomenon in question was first considered from a scientific point of view. This is done to find that point in history where a question first became relevant to human beings and to explore why this was.

The dramatic element is central because each pedagogical case is constructed around a developed dramaturgy with an initial question that catches the students’ attention and awakens their interest. It also implies that each pedagogical case can be described in text as a kind of drama and thus be passed on for others to stage. In this way, it is argued, we could over time amass a large collection of educational dramas to stage by teachers.

¹ Called “staging lessons” on the website lehrkunst.org, pedagogical case is more connected to established vocabulary in English and covers the two salient factors: it is a “piece” (Stück) or case of some educational content, and it is pedagogical in the sense of being concerned with teaching for understanding and development (ie. Bildung).

Close to 60 pedagogical cases are available (as of spring 2023) at lehrkunst.org. They cover almost every subject-area and are primarily focused on students at the secondary- and upper secondary level. None, however, seem to be concerned with vocational education or to be based on a vocational task that is transformed into a general educational task. Examples of pedagogical cases are Aesop's fables, Geometrical proofs with Euclid, Dostoyevsky's Grand Inquisitor, Goethe's metamorphoses of plants and Mörike's Mozart. A couple, The Walk with Robert Walser and Universal grammar with Noam Chomsky, are available in English. Almost all contain a brief synopsis and then a longer description covering between 20 and 70 pages where the case is described more extensively. Each pedagogical case is normally between 10 and 25 lessons and has been developed in cooperation with colleagues and researchers.

The field of vocational didactics contains at least two areas that clearly overlap with "the art of teaching":

1. Many vocational tasks easily integrate the exemplary and the genetic elements of "the art of teaching" since most of them have developed within a concrete context.
2. Vocational training and vocational courses are often given in blocks and periods rather than single lessons, something that is generally conducive to pedagogical cases.

Theoretical perspectives and method

The study compares and discusses didactical frameworks incorporating case study research as a way of expanding theoretical perspectives further (Tyson, 2017). The research design is based in Flyvbjerg's phronetic perspective (Flyvbjerg, 2001) where the aim of social science research is to enable wiser practice. Methodologically the study is largely an amalgam of theoretical research and case study research where the two case studies were documented using interviews and action research respectively.

None of the cases presented were explicitly developed within the framework of "the art of teaching" rather they are presented as cases that could profitably be contextualized within that framework and thereby expanded on. Given the format of the paper, the cases are presented in condensed form.

Case study #1 Bookbinding

The first case focuses briefly on how a vocational task can be transformed into an "art-of-teaching" case. It is taken from the craft of bookbinding and was documented through a series of four action research cycles. Each cycle encompassed 14 lessons of 80-minute length (given twice a week for 7 weeks) and involved both lectures and the practical work of making the books in question. The participating students were around 15 years of age at the time and in Swedish secondary school (9th grade).

In bookbinding there are several different kinds of books that can be made. These vary over time and across cultures. In choosing which books to include in a bookbinding project it is possible to create a contrasting effect that illustrates powerfully the difference that culture, materials, and tools have in the shaping of an object.

In this case the standard European book-format, the codex, is compared to the East-Asian book as it was traditionally made in China and Japan. It turns out that down to the details these craft-pieces are opposites. Owing to differences in the fibres used to make paper, European paper has always been comparatively thick whereas East-Asian paper is generally very thin. European books have hard covers made of cardboard or wood; East-Asian books have soft covers. European books have the paper folded at the spine, East-Asian books have it folded at what, from a European perspective, constitutes the books front. The text is written horizontally in European books and vertically in East-Asian books. It is written with hard feather-pens in European books and with soft brushes in East-Asian books. Space does not permit a full

exploration of the case, suffice it to say that by contrasting these two cultural artifacts an exemplary, dramatic, and genetic effect is possible to achieve.

In this case the aim was to take an element of a traditional craft and make it available to students involved in general education, i.e. to enrich their education with a task from a vocational field that was unusually rich in Bildung-potential.

Case study #2 Making an iron cube

In the process of documenting the vocational education biography of crafts-master Wolfgang B. (cf. Tyson 2015) a longer narrative was recorded where he spoke of a task his father, who worked in the metal-industry in Stuttgart, gave him for his 16th birthday (fully discussed from a vocational didactical perspective in Tyson 2016). In the narrative he describes how he received a rough iron cube and some tools as a gift with the task of making a perfectly angular cube with perfectly smooth surfaces. In the process, not only did he develop the skills in question but also describes how he gained a wider understanding of the materials and tools in question as well as developing dispositional capacities such as care, exactness, and meticulousness. Finally, he was also introduced to fields of knowledge implicitly present in the task. These ranged from geometry (the platonic bodies) to physics (the metal expanding and deforming from the heat of the hands) to cultural history (the Vikings and their steel as well as their settlement at Hedeby). In this way the case illustrates how a particular vocational task, treated in a pedagogical way (i.e., from a Bildung-perspective, eliciting as much meaningfulness as can be imagined from it), can become everything that “the art of teaching” conceptualizes and more. Whereas the pedagogical cases developed thus far mostly engage with teaching for a deeper understanding this case also includes development of dispositions and skills together with a wider, understanding-oriented contextualization of the task.

Results

This study and discussion are, perhaps, a first, minor, contribution to the enrichment of vocational didactics through an important and well researched Bildung-oriented didactical perspective. Parallel to this it might also serve to highlight the potential of vocational tasks to contribute also to general education and to “the art of teaching” in a more general sense, thereby demonstrating that vocational education, far from being “just for those learning a job”, contains aspects and elements that are of a much wider importance from a didactical or curriculum point of view.

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Biographical notes

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